

ELECTRICAL, THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC ELASTOMER COMPOSITES CONTAINING CARBON FILLERS

Rajesh Theravalappil¹, Petr Svoboda²

¹ Center for Refining and Petrochemicals, Research Institute
King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia.

² Faculty of Technology, Department of Polymer Engineering,
Tomas Bata University in Zlin, Zlin, Czech Republic.

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Highlights

- **Soft TPE composites**
- **Electrical conductivity**
- **Thermal conductivity**
- **Hardness**
- **Flammability**
- **Thermal stability**

Thermoplastic Elastomers (TPEs)

Materials with processability (i.e., by melt processing) of a thermoplastic and elastic behavior of a vulcanized (chemically cross-linked) conventional elastomers.

Phase structure of thermoplastic elastomers.

DE, S.K.; WHITE, J.R., *Rubber Technologist's Handbook*, Shropshire: Rapra Technology Limited, 2001. ISBN 1-85957-262-6.

Polyethylene/poly(α -olefin) copolymers

Prepared via metallocene polymerization – CGCT.
Substitute for EPDM, SBCs, PVC and EVA.

e.g.: Ethylene-octene copolymer (EOC)

- Good filler acceptance
- Available in the form of pellets
- Easy mixing and processability
- Light weight, more flexible parts
- Excellent elastic and impact properties
- Compatible with most olefins and excellent clarity

Overview

EG – Expandable graphite
CF – carbon fibres
MWCNT – multiwall carbon nanotubes

DC conductivity of EOC/ CF, EOC/ MWCNT & EOC/Graphite composites.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0(\phi - \phi_c)^t$$

Filler	σ_0 (S cm ⁻¹)	t
Graphite	1.33×10^4	1.77
CF	83.3	1.9
MWCNT	8.33	1.4

Alternating Current (AC) conductivity of EOC/graphite composites.

AC conductivity of EOC/CF & EOC/MWCNT composites

σ_{ac} at 10^4 Hz

Thermal Conductivity

Experimental setup for thermal conductivity measurement.

$$\lambda = \frac{A_1 \delta K_1}{S}$$

Thermal capacity of the central brass cylinder,
 $K_1 = 94.107 \text{ J K}^{-1}$
Area of measured cylinder, S in m^2
Thickness of sample = δ

Thermal Conductivity of EOC/CF, EOC/MWCNT &, EOC/Graphite composites

SEM of 20 wt% of a) EOC/Graphite, b) EOC/CF & c) EOC/MWCNT composites

Hardness of EOC composites

Flammability test of EOC/Graphite composites

Tensile curves of EOC/MWCNT and EOC/CF composites

Thermogravimetric analysis of EOC/MWCNT and EOC/CF composites

Thank you

King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals
kfupm.edu.sa